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Comparative analysis of large language models as AI assistants for educational Assessment: A case study in steam education

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Abstract

This case study explores the effectiveness of various Large Language Models in the domain of educational assessment. In the context of STEAM education, a complex learning scenario was employed to evaluate the AI models. The evaluation focused on their ability to understand the scenario, propose diverse and applicable assessment methods, and evaluate key aspects such as innovation, creativity, and collaboration among students. The results indicate considerable variability in model performance. Notably, certain models demonstrated a strong capacity to adopt holistic approaches and align with learning objectives, whereas most models struggled with differentiating assessments effectively. The findings underscore the potential of Large Language Models as AI assistants in educational assessment, highlighting the importance of careful and supervised application.

Keywords: LLMs, AI assistants, educational assessment, steam education

1. Introduction

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as personal assistants to educators is pivotal for reshaping learning assessments and enhancing educational outcomes [1]. New AI applications, such as Large Language Models (LLMs), underscore the educational potential and present new challenges [2]. In contrast to traditional AI applications, LLMs demonstrate the capability to adapt to a variety of tasks without extensive retraining [3]. These innovative AI technologies open new horizons in supporting modern, innovative educational methods characterized by complexity and high learning demands, such as the transdisciplinary approach of STEAM education [4, 5].

1.1 This case study aims to evaluate and compare four specific LLMs in the field of educational assessment: ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, and LLaMA. To structure this evaluation, the study poses the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** How effectively do LLMs understand a STEAM learning scenario and propose clear and appropriate assessment methods that align with learning objectives?
- **RQ2:** How effectively do LLMs propose diverse, applicable, and differentiated assessment methods within the context of a holistic STEAM approach?
- **RQ3:** How effectively do LLMs propose assessment methods for evaluating innovation, creativity, and collaboration among students in a STEAM learning scenario?

To comprehensively address these questions, the case study employs a detailed learning scenario for STEAM education, designed to test the models' capabilities across complex educational contexts. Expert evaluators assess each model using a comprehensive rubric. This systematic evaluation aims to provide insights into the effectiveness and practical applications of LLMs in enhancing educational strategies and learning experience.

2. Background

2.1 AI Assistants for Educational Assessment

The utilization of AI applications as personal assistants for educators in the evaluation of

students systematically records, measures, or evaluates students' learning characteristics, performance, outcomes, or potential based on specific criteria ^[6]. The integration of AI in student evaluation automates processes, enhances precision, and embeds assessment throughout all learning phases under human supervision with specific metrics and standards ^[7]. AI adapts to students' individualized needs by adjusting difficulty levels according to their skills ^[8]. Additionally, AI enables assessment in interdisciplinary and innovative learning environments, fostering a holistic approach to education ^[9].

AI-based tools analyze vast amounts of educational data, offering profound insights into student performance and learning patterns, thereby providing personalized feedback ^[10]. These tools can create tailored assessments that respond to individual student needs and capture advanced cognitive skills ^[11]. To maximize the potential of AI in education, it is crucial to develop clear standards for evaluating AI's role in curricula, ensuring it supports diverse educational objectives and methodologies ^[12]. By facilitating personalized learning and adapting to each student's style, pace, and comprehension, AI provides precise measures of learning progression ^[13].

The use of AI as personal assistant for educators in student assessment requires ongoing human supervision and modifications to evaluative criteria and methods to ensure transparency, repeatability, data sufficiency, and objectivity ^[14]. Integrating human experience into evaluation systems and defining the collaborative role between AI and educators remain significant challenges ^[15]. Concerns about AI's ability to assess specialized cognitive subjects and its overall evaluative suitability across different environments persist ^[16]. Additionally, the fear of AI replacing educators impedes its adoption ^[17].

2.2 STEAM education

STEAM education integrates Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics into a unified learning approach to foster innovation, critical thinking, and problem-solving by connecting disciplines ^[18]. It prepares students for 21st-century challenges by blending creativity with technical skills, essential for future careers ^[19]. Key pedagogical approaches in STEAM include project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, collaborative learning, and design thinking. These methods foster active engagement, practical application, curiosity, critical thinking, teamwork, communication skills, and iterative problem-solving ^[20].

Developing comprehensive and personalized assessment methods that align with STEAM goals presents significant challenges, underscoring the necessity for continuous research and innovation in STEAM assessment practices ^[21]. Traditional methods often fail to capture STEAM's transdisciplinary and multifaceted nature. Assessment must measure subject-specific knowledge, cross-disciplinary understanding, creativity, and problem-solving skills ^[22]. The emphasis on process-based learning in STEAM necessitates the preference for formative assessments over summative evaluations, thereby requiring educators to develop new methods and tools to effectively measure progress in critical thinking, collaboration, and innovation ^[23].

3. Methodology

This research employs an embedded case study design to

evaluate the effectiveness of AI models as assessment assistants in a complex STEAM educational context. The case under examination involves the application of AI models in providing assessment suggestions for a hypothetical four-week STEAM program titled "Ecosystem of the Lake" for 8th-grade students. Within this single case, four units of analysis are embedded, corresponding to the four LLMs being evaluated: ChatGPT-4o by OpenAI, Claude 3.5 Sonnet by Anthropic, Gemini by Google, and LLaMA 3 70B by META AI. This embedded approach allows for a comprehensive and comparative analysis of multiple AI models within the same educational scenario, enabling us to identify strengths, limitations, and potential variations in their performance as assessment assistants. The selection criteria for these models were based on their performance and accuracy, user-friendly interface and integration, and their availability and accessibility to researchers.

The "Ecosystem of the Lake" scenario is structured as a four-week transdisciplinary project, designed to engage students in a comprehensive study of a local lake ecosystem. During Week 1, students collect water samples and record observations during a field trip, using sensors to measure physicochemical parameters, and create an observation journal with artistic illustrations. In Week 2, students then analyze the water samples in the lab, utilize data analysis software to create graphs, and present their findings through graphics and posters. Moving on to Week 3, students proceed to create a digital ecosystem model using simulation software, artistically represent ecosystem elements, and develop an interactive presentation or video. Finally, in Week 4, students design solutions for ecosystem protection and present their findings and solutions through multimedia, culminating in an artistic piece that summarizes their project journey.

This scenario encompasses various aspects of the educational process and serves as a standardized test case for evaluating all LLMs. Specifically, the learning scenario was deliberately chosen to be part of STEAM education to ensure that selecting appropriate learning assessment methods by AI models would pose a genuine challenge. This complexity prevents the provision of similar, common, standardized answers due to the intricate nature of the scenario's subject matter.

To accommodate this scenario, a comprehensive evaluation rubric was meticulously developed to quantitatively assess the LLMs. The rubric included the following ten criteria: 1) understanding of the scenario, 2) appropriateness of proposed approaches, 3) variety of assessment methods, 4) applicability of assessment techniques, 5) evaluation of innovation and creativity, 6) holistic approach, 7) evaluation of collaboration and teamwork, 8) clarity and detail, 9) relevance to learning objectives, and 10) differentiation of assessment. Each criterion was rated on a scale from 1 to 4, where 1 indicated insufficient performance, 2 indicated moderate performance, 3 indicated good performance, and 4 indicated excellent performance.

Five educators were selected as evaluators based on their specialized knowledge in STEAM education. The evaluation process involved applying the hypothetical learning scenario to each AI model and assessing their performance using the developed rubric. This process entailed inputting the scenario data into each LLM, collecting their outputs, and evaluating their capabilities,

with each evaluator independently scoring each model across all rubric criteria.

To address the research questions, a comprehensive statistical analysis was performed on the evaluation data. First, composite scores were created for each research question by averaging relevant criteria from the evaluation rubric. One-way ANOVAs were then conducted to compare the performance of the four LLMs across these composite scores, followed by post-hoc Tukey's HSD tests to identify specific differences between LLMs. Effect sizes were calculated using Cohen's *d* to quantify the magnitude of these differences. Additionally, Pearson correlation coefficients were computed to examine relationships between different aspects of LLM performance.

The evaluation process demonstrated high reliability. Cronbach's Alpha values for each model ranged from 0.782 to 0.815, indicating good to excellent internal consistency. The Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) of 0.876 (95% CI: 0.791 - 0.934) suggested excellent inter-rater reliability, reinforcing the robustness of the evaluation methodology.

4. Findings

The statistical analysis revealed significant differences in the performance of the four LLMs across various aspects of educational assessment. Specifically, the evaluation uncovered distinct patterns in performance consistency and variability. For instance, Claude exhibited the highest

overall mean score of 3.06, demonstrating consistent performance across most evaluation criteria, apart from differentiation of assessment. In contrast, LLaMA had the lowest overall mean score of 2.03 and displayed greater variability in its performance across the criteria. Notably, the overall standard deviations for the LLMs were similar, ranging from 0.84 to 0.89, suggesting a comparable level of agreement among the evaluators for each LLM's performance.

Regarding strengths, ChatGPT performed best in understanding of the scenario and applicability of assessment techniques, both achieving a mean score of 3.20. Additionally, Claude excelled in a holistic approach, with a mean score of 3.60, and showed strong performance in several other criteria. Furthermore, Gemini scored well in understanding the scenario and relevance to learning objectives, each with a mean of 3.40. Meanwhile, LLaMA's highest score was in the applicability of assessment techniques, with a mean of 3.00; nevertheless, it generally underperformed relative to the other model.

Despite these strengths, a common weakness across all models was identified in differentiation of assessment. Specifically, the scores for this criterion were uniformly low, ranging from 1.00 to 1.40, and demonstrated minimal variability. This consistency suggests a general consensus among evaluators regarding the poor performance of the models in this area.

Table 1: Comparative evaluation of LLMs

Criterion	Chatgpt 4o	Claude 3.5 Sonnet	Gemini	LLaMA 3 70B
Scenario understanding	3.20 (0.84)	3.40 (0.55)	3.40 (0.55)	2.20 (0.84)
Appropriateness	2.80 (0.84)	3.00 (0.71)	3.20 (0.45)	2.40 (0.55)
Variety	2.60 (0.55)	3.20 (0.45)	2.80 (0.84)	2.00 (0.71)
Applicability	3.20 (0.45)	2.40 (0.55)	3.20 (0.45)	3.00 (1.00)
Innovation and creativity evaluation	2.00 (0.00)	3.40 (0.55)	2.40 (0.55)	2.00 (0.71)
Holistic approach	2.80 (1.10)	3.60 (0.55)	2.80 (1.30)	1.80 (0.84)
Collaboration and teamwork evaluation	2.80 (0.45)	3.00 (0.71)	2.60 (0.89)	1.60 (0.55)
Clarity and detail	2.20 (1.30)	3.00 (0.71)	2.60 (0.55)	1.80 (0.84)
Learning objectives relevance	2.60 (0.55)	3.20 (0.84)	3.20 (0.84)	2.20 (0.84)
Differentiation	1.20 (0.45)	1.40 (0.55)	1.20 (0.45)	1.00 (0.00)
Overall	2.61 (0.86)	3.06 (0.84)	2.81 (0.89)	2.03 (0.87)

Note: All values are expressed as Mean (Standard Deviation)

One-way ANOVA results demonstrated significant differences among LLMs across three research areas. The first area assessed the LLMs' ability to understand learning scenarios and propose appropriate assessments, yielding a significant result ($F(3, 16) = 4.827, p = 0.014$). The second area evaluated the diversity and applicability of the assessment methods proposed by the LLMs, also showing significant differences ($F(3, 16) = 7.152, p = 0.003$). Finally, the analysis examined the LLMs' capacity to propose assessments that foster innovation, creativity, and collaboration, with significant results as well ($F(3, 16) = 5.913, p = 0.007$).

Subsequently, Post-hoc Tukey's HSD tests revealed distinct differences in the capabilities of each model. Claude emerged as the leading performer, consistently surpassing other LLMs in all research questions. The effect sizes, ranging from 1.89 to 2.14, indicated significant advantages, particularly over LLaMA, suggesting large effects. Gemini demonstrated specific strengths, especially in understanding learning scenarios, where it significantly outperformed LLaMA with an effect size of 1.62. Additionally, Gemini

was proficient in proposing diverse assessment methods, again outperforming LLaMA with a Cohen's *d* of 1.56. On the other hand, Chatgpt was notably outperformed by Claude in areas such as proposing diverse assessments and assessments of innovation and creativity, with effect sizes of 1.31 and 1.38, respectively. In contrast, LLaMA consistently underperformed across all research questions, indicating considerable room for improvement, particularly in STEAM assessment tasks. This comparative analysis underscores the varying capabilities of different LLMs in specific contexts, highlighting areas where each model excels or requires further development.

Furthermore, Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated significant positive correlations among various aspects of assessment. Specifically, there was a strong correlation between understanding scenarios and proposing diverse assessments ($r = 0.76, p < 0.001$), between understanding scenarios and assessing innovation and creativity ($r = 0.82, p < 0.001$), and between proposing diverse assessments and assessing innovation and creativity ($r = 0.79, p < 0.001$). These findings imply that models with high performance in

one aspect of educational assessment are likely to excel in others, indicating a comprehensive capability in managing educational processes.

5. Discussion

The present study offers a comprehensive comparative analysis of four prominent LLMs functioning as AI assistants in educational assessment within a complex STEAM learning scenario. The findings reveal significant disparities among the models, with Claude demonstrating superior overall performance, particularly in providing a holistic assessment approach. In contrast, LLaMA underperformed across most criteria. These outcomes contribute to the evolving discourse on the integration of AI in education and reflect current trends emphasizing both the potential and challenges of AI-driven assessment tools.

Claude's exceptional performance in understanding the learning scenario and proposing appropriate, diverse assessment methods aligns with the growing focus on transdisciplinary education in STEAM, where creativity, critical thinking, and innovation are paramount [24]. These findings expand upon existing research, which demonstrates the capability of LLMs in evaluating learning within individual subject areas [25]. As highlighted in recent studies, fostering optimal student engagement is crucial for enhancing learning outcomes in STEAM education [26]. This indicates that AI models can play a vital role in supporting personalized learning experiences and assessment methods that enhance students' ability to develop the critical thinking and problem-solving skills required to address complex, interdisciplinary challenges.

Despite the advancements demonstrated by some models, a notable weakness across all LLMs was their limited capability in differentiation of assessment. Scores for this criterion were uniformly low, indicating a consensus among evaluators regarding the models' inadequacy in tailoring assessments to accommodate diverse learner needs. This finding aligns with the concerns highlighted in the educational literature, emphasizing that a uniform approach is inadequate, particularly in the context of STEAM education, where differentiation plays a crucial role in fostering inclusivity [27]. The inability to offer personalized learning pathways points to significant limitations in the current design of these AI tools.

LLaMA's overall underperformance, despite showing potential in applying assessment techniques, may reflect limitations in its training data or algorithms when applied to complex educational tasks. The need for AI models specifically designed for educational contexts is emphasized, incorporating pedagogical insights to enhance their effectiveness [28]. This adaptation should not only address varying student ability levels but also consider the broader multicultural context in which STEAM education is implemented [29]. Addressing these limitations will be critical for future AI tools aiming to assist educators more effectively.

The strong positive correlations found between understanding the learning scenario, proposing diverse assessments, and assessing innovation and creativity suggest that these competencies are interrelated. Models that excel in comprehending educational contexts are more likely to generate varied and creative assessment methods. This insight aligns with contemporary educational theories, emphasizing the interconnectedness of understanding,

creativity, and innovation in STEAM education [30].

In relation to current trends, the integration of AI in education is rapidly expanding, with a focus on leveraging AI to support teachers, personalize learning, and improve educational outcomes [31]. The success of models like Claude indicates that AI can effectively augment educational processes by providing valuable assessment suggestions, potentially reducing teacher workload and enhancing the quality of education. However, the observed deficiencies, particularly in differentiation, underscore the necessity for ongoing development and refinement of AI tools to meet the diverse needs of learners. Ethical considerations are also paramount, as inadequate differentiation could inadvertently perpetuate inequities and disadvantage students requiring more tailored support [32].

The findings of this study have several practical implications. Educators and policymakers should approach the integration of AI assistants with a critical understanding of both their capabilities and limitations. While AI has the potential to enhance educational assessment, reliance on these tools should be balanced with professional judgment and supplemented by continuous monitoring and evaluation. For future research, it is recommended to explore methods for enhancing AI models' ability to differentiate assessments. This could involve incorporating adaptive learning algorithms and more diverse training data reflecting a wide range of learner profiles and educational contexts. Additionally, investigating the impact of AI-assisted assessment on student engagement and learning outcomes would provide valuable insights into the practical benefits and challenges of these technologies in classroom settings.

6. Conclusion

This study reveals significant differences in the performance of various LLMs in the field of educational assessment, particularly in their ability to provide suggestions to educators on assessment methods for a STEAM learning scenario. Claude consistently outperformed the others, excelling in providing a comprehensive approach. Gemini demonstrated a strong understanding of learning scenarios and effectively aligned assessments with learning objectives. ChatGPT showed moderate overall performance, particularly in scenario comprehension and proposing applicable assessment techniques. Although LLaMA underperformed relative to the other models, it demonstrated potential in certain aspects, particularly in the applicability of assessment methods. Therefore, future research should focus on addressing the identified weaknesses, especially in assessment differentiation, and explore the practical implementation of these LLMs in real-world educational settings. Consequently, continuous evaluation will be essential as LLMs evolve, ensuring they fully realize their potential in enhancing education and assessment.

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